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**International Scientific Conference on
“Transformations of Postwar Europe: Medicine,
Bodies and Technologies”, Sofia, May 27-30, 2024**

Abstract: *The review presents the international scientific conference “Transformations of Postwar Europe: Medicine, Bodies and Technologies” which was held in Sofia between 27th and 30th May 2024 as part of the project “Taming the European Leviathan: The Legacy of Post-War Medicine and the Common Good” [H2020 ERC-2019- SyG; GAID: 854503], funded by the European Research Council, under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, and organized by the Medical Anthropology Department at IEFSEM – BAS.*

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The international scientific conference “Transformations of Postwar Europe: Medicine, Bodies and Technologies” was held at the Czech Centre in Sofia between 27th and 30th May 2024. The event took place as part of the project “Taming the European Leviathan: The Legacy of Post-War Medicine and the Common Good” [H2020 ERC-2019- SyG; GAID: 854503], funded by the European Research Council, under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, and organized by the Medical Anthropology Department at IEFSEM – BAS. The programme included over 40 researchers from different academic institutions across 12 countries who presented their original research inspired by several thematic circles: Technologies of (Self)Governmentality: (Self)Care and (Self)Control; Technologies of the Collective Body; Utopias, Delusions, Risks; Visualizations and Representations.

The forum brought together world-renowned scholars and at the same time attracted many young researchers working in various fields of the humanities, social and applied sciences, including history, ethnology,

sociology, philosophy, law, ethics, economics, architecture, etc. Three key note presentations and ten thematic panels were organized within its framework, offering both an interdisciplinary floor for expression and an opportunity for in-depth and dynamic discussions.

The event was opened on May 27 by Vihra Baeva, the Scientific Secretary of the IEFSEM – BAS, followed by Anelia Kassabova, the Principal Investigator in the Bulgarian team of the “Leviathan” project and head of the Medical Anthropology Department. They welcomed all the speakers and guests and presented the main aim of the conference: “contributing to a deeper understanding of the changing concept of care and hence the changes of relationships between the individual, the society, and the state. The emphasis is on the interconnectedness of Europe, on the entangled history that involves different forms of interaction – intersections, exchanges, competition, conflicts”.¹

The opening ceremony continued with the first keynote presentation by Agnieszka Kościańska from the University of Warsaw, introduced by Anelia Kassabova. Drawing on a historical perspective, Kościańska discussed so-called natural family planning in Poland. The focus was on the transnational influence of the Catholic Church in framing it as medically informed expert knowledge. This perspective reinforces *conservative narratives* on issues such as sexuality and reproduction, positively framing the male figure in a sphere typically dominated by female responsabilization, and constructing it as a corrective for ‘deviant’ female behavior. The paper attracted significant interest as it also addressed contemporary developments in the context of the unfolding large-scale anti-gender movements, which allowed participants in the discussion to share and comment on their local experiences through a comparative perspective.

Kristina Popova introduced the second keynote speaker of the event – Heike Karge from the University of Graz, whose presentation took place on 28 May. Karge’s presentation also adopted a comparative research approach, but focused on a different range of questions. This time, the issue of Cold War-era psychiatric discourses came into focus, and more specifically – the psyche of the soldier and treatment for the psychopathological effects of World War II on those serving on the front line. She emphasized the points of transfer, intersection and divergence in diagnostic strategies on both sides of the Iron Curtain. Through her

¹ For more information about the idea of the event, as well as the full programme: <https://iefem.bas.bg/mezhdnarodna-konferenca-transfor.html>

case study, Heike Karge illustrated the dynamics of numerous heterogeneous processes that underlie the conceptualization of an experience as trauma(tic) and “tame” the exogenesis of war traumatism. Following her analysis, it can be concluded that such discourses gradually normalize this type of disorders, but only insofar as they pre-assign them as *temporary*. In this sense, the notion of long-lasting effects is delegitimized by psychiatric discourses themselves, and these possible effects seem implicitly repositioned in the realm of individual dispositions.

Gergana Mircheva from the Institute of Sociology and Philosophy at BAS delivered her keynote speech on the next day of the conference, introduced by Daniela Koleva. Mircheva drew the audience’s attention to another case of normative construction of (ab)normality from the second half of the 20th century in Bulgaria. Her long-standing interest focuses on the conceptualization of autism and its definition and treatment as a condition with a peripheral presence in expert knowledge. Mircheva examined the diagnostic approaches to autism during this period as unstable categories framed by *psycho-medical scripts*, which in practice are subject to transnational circulation. In this context, a critical analysis of the positioning of this type of experience in view of the ideological significance of childhood, for example, is extremely important. The lecture again opened up an opportunity for in-depth discussion, with some of the questions revolving around the lack of first-person testimonies from the suffering subjects themselves, as well as around current issues faced by people diagnosed with the condition. The discussion was further supported by the participation of representatives of the psychiatric field who worked during the same period, including Ignat Petrov, MD.

The three keynote speeches were preceded by a number of papers presented in thematic panels, offering multiple approaches to the research topics set by the conference theme. The first panel, entitled *Medical Ethics and the Notion of Patient’s Agency in Post-war Europe*, featured three scholars who addressed different aspects of ethical and legal debates around the role of expert knowledge and citizenship. This included the medicalization of death in Hungary (Judit Sándor, Central European University) and the Netherlands (Mária Éva Földes, Erasmus University Rotterdam), and the secularization of medical deontology in post-war Poland (Ulf Schmidt, University of Hamburg).

The second panel, entitled *Between Traditional Healing Practices and Alternative Medicine: Science and Critique*, focused on alternative narratives by bringing together several approaches towards the processes of transference and adoption of various spiritual and therapeutic practic-

es. The discussions were particularly interesting as they demonstrated the reflexive attitude of the panelists, each of whom is directly involved in these practices in one form or another: by engaged participant observation during shamanic healing rituals (Emil Antonov, IEFSEM – BAS); via (auto)ethnographic research in the field of Ayurvedic philosophy (Alžběta Wolfová, University of Economics in Prague); and through the professional exercise of Japanese psychotherapeutic practices (Velizara Chervenková, Osaka University).

Deviant Bodies, Healing Minds: Expert Knowledge and the Medicalization and Demedicalization of the Suffering Subject was the title of the next session. Here, the authors presented their work on several forms of so-called social pathologies, along with the spectrum of normative discourses and endogenous practices applied to their ‘taming’. Tiago Pires (IEFSEM – BAS) addressed the field of Italian ethnopsychiatry and the culturally based methods for the treatment of mental disorders. Jakub Strelec (Institute for the History of Medicine and Ethics in Medicine at Charité, Berlin) and Vjačeslav Glazov (Charles University in Prague), on the other hand, focused on themes related to criminality using the example of socialist Czechoslovakia. Strelec did so through the lens of forensic psychiatry and the projects for prediction of risky behavior, while Glazov examined the framing of the notion of juvenile delinquency as an ideological challenge during late socialism.

The participants in the panel *Crossing Borders, Transgressing Boundaries* illustrated the diversity of forms in which the circulation of ideas, subjects, and practices occurs on both sides of the Iron/Nylon Curtain. Under the chairmanship of Alexa Geisthövel (Institute for the History of Medicine and Ethics in Medicine at Charité, Berlin), several issues were brought into focus: the so-called *traveling Pavlovism* reflected in the educational programmes developed by two leading figures working on one side of the Berlin Wall, but offering different readings of it (Kristina Popova, IEFSEM – BAS); the labor migration of medical personnel as a strategy for strengthening ideological influence in “Third World” countries (Mila Maeva, IEFSEM – BAS); and the contact between the Western pharmaceutical industry and the Eastern drug market (Volker Hess (Institute for the History of Medicine and Ethics in Medicine at Charité, Berlin).

The second day of the scientific forum continued with more papers in four thematic panels. *Nature as Technology: Health Infrastructures and Symbolic Mapping of the Social Space* was one of the sub-themes that problematized various aspects of public welfare policies in socialist

Bulgaria. Slava Savova (IEFSEM – BAS) examined the structuring of space in balneological centers and public baths, emphasizing their implicit gender dimensions that frame female corporeality primarily as reproductive power. The question of the governmentality of leisure and the ideological framing of sport as a universally applicable method for maintaining good health (both for the individual and for the population) was the focus of a presentation by Nevena Dimitrova (IEFSEM – BAS). Ekaterina Tsoleva (ETH Zürich) continued this line by focusing more specifically on pioneer camps.

They were joined by Sławomir Łotysz (Institute of the History of Science of the Polish Academy of Sciences) – a participant in the sixth panel of the conference *Management of Risk: Care for the Collective Body and Responsibilization of the Self*. His paper analyzed mainstream media narratives in the coverage of the HIV/AIDS crisis in Poland which contextualized the latter as the result of the deviant behavior of a cluster of marginalized groups – a crisis that contradicts the image built by the socialist propaganda apparatus. Łotysz traces both these discourses and the work of medical circles to overcome their negative effects.

The seventh panel, *Finding Cures and Treating Bodies behind and beyond the Iron Curtain*, delved into the research and treatment history of several more socially significant diseases and conditions. Fruzsina Müller (Institute for the History of Medicine and Ethics in Medicine at Charité, Berlin) traced the changes in the perception of syphilis infection following the discovery of a method for its mass antibiotic treatment via penicillin. Progress in the treatment of Down's syndrome through the application of cell therapies since the 1960s at an international scale was the topic presented by Paul van Trigt (Leiden University). Georgi Todorov (IEFSEM – BAS) focused on a Bulgarian case, addressing the controversial application of therapies using psychotropic medications in institutions for children with mental disorders.

This line of research was continued by the participants in the next panel, *Institutional Care and Social Marginalization in Post-War Europe: Case Studies*. It featured four papers discussing different approaches and institutional care policies for several segments of the population, with some focusing on childcare. José Luis Aguilar López-Barajas presented his joint work with Natalia Jarska (both from the Institute of History, Czech Academy of Sciences) exploring the reception and application of John Bowlby's theories in the setting of the mass introduction of state-run nurseries in Poland and the GDR. David Peace (University of Hamburg) recounted several cases from post-war Britain of newborns

placed in a reception center for children from “problem families”, explaining the eugenic programmes behind such institutions. Samuel Fély (CEMS of EHESS) presented an ethnographic study on contemporary early diagnosis processes for children with development difficulties, stressing the forms of pre-school segregation in France. Inxhi Brisku (IEFSEM – BAS) drew attention to another aspect of institutionalization - elder care in Albania during the early years of the socialist regime.

The final day of the event included two more scientific sessions. Z. Selen Artan (Marmara University in Istanbul) examined a series of reproductive laws in post-war Turkey, explicating the biopolitical narratives behind them, while Ivana Dobrivojević Tomić (Institute for Contemporary History in Belgrade) presented on the topic of contraception in Yugoslavia. She drew particular attention to the dissonance between practitioners and health services attempts at promoting contraceptives and the population’s reluctance to use them. Barna Szamosi (Eszterházy Károly Catholic University at the Institute of English, American and German Studies in Eger and the Center for Ethics and Law in Biomedicine) discussed the eugenic legacy of genetic counseling in socialist Hungary, used as a risk management strategy. Their papers were part of the panel *Population Planning and Reproductive Policies:(Self) Care as (Self) Control*.

Beyond the Engineering of the “New Socialist Man”: Institutionalized Practices and Ideological Concepts was the title of the last thematic session dedicated to examining several utopian notions of modernity. Denitsa Nencheva (IEFSEM – BAS) presented the transformations of the ideas behind the concept of “anthropotechnics”. Georgeta Nazarska (University of Library Studies and IT) introduced her historiographical research on the so-called “Program for the Complex Study of Man and his Brain”, linking it to ideas of harmonious development of the personality. Yana Yancheva (IEFSEM – BAS) chose another subject though which to illustrate the exemplary image of the socialist man – that of the comprehensively developed child. Martin Kuhar (Division for the History of Medical Sciences Croatian Academy of Sciences and Arts) commented on the use of eugenic projects to increase the population in the Independent State of Croatia, dating from the end of the first half and the beginning of the second half of the 20th century.

Last but not least, the programme included papers by Iwona Boruszkowska and Kinga Siewior (Jagiellonian University in Cracow); Veronika Stoyanova (University of Kent); Klejdi Këlliçi (University of Tirana); Tatjana Enderić (University of Zagreb Faculty of Humanities and

Social Sciences); and Marie Hintnausová (Charles University in Prague, Faculty of Humanities), who were unable to attend the conference, but along with the other participants, will have the opportunity to develop their ideas in a planned forthcoming volume.

The lectures, presentations, and discussions accompanying all scientific sessions demonstrated the wide range of issues and questions that make the the legacy of post-war Europe increasingly relevant. The focus was on the interweaving of fields such as medicine, technology, social policy, and more, as well as on the explication of techniques of governmentality and tools for social engineering from both local and transnational perspectives. This has allowed for critical reflection on grand narratives and official discourses sometimes manifest and other times elusive to the normative gaze. The approaches identified by the participants and the scholarly dialogue between them highlighted multiple possibilities for thinking about these issues in comparative perspective, both synchronically and diachronically.